

tients in whom BP developed before malignancy, at presentation and during subsequent follow-up for up to 3 years, will lead to the detection of tumours, some of which may be potentially treatable.

References

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BEYOND EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE

From science to art

"The ward was full, so I put him in my room as he was moribund and screaming and I did not want to wake the ward. I examined him. He had obvious gross bilateral crepitations and a severe pleural rub. I thought the latter was the cause of the pain and screaming. I had no morphia, just aspirin, which had no effect. I felt desperate. I knew very little Russian then and there was no one in the ward who did."

"I finally instinctively sat down on the bed and took him in my arms, and the screaming stopped almost at once. He died peacefully in my arms a few hours later. It was not the pleurisy that caused the screaming, but loneliness. It was a wonderful education about the care of the dying. I was ashamed of my misdiagnosis and kept the story a secret."

Quoted from the last page of Cochrane Collaboration on evidence-based medicine

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